

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some thioacids by tetrabutylammonium tribromide

V. K. Chouhan and Vinita Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, India

Manuscript received 18 July 2003, revised 3 November 2004, accepted 9 December 2004

The oxidation of some thioacids viz. thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids by tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) has been studied in acetic acid. The reaction is first order with respect to TBATB. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics were observed with respect to the reductants. The reaction has been studied in solvents of different compositions of acetic acid and water. The solvent composition effect has been analysed using Grunwald-Weinstein equation. A mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate complex in the pre-equilibrium and its subsequent decomposition in slow step has been proposed.

Tetraalkylammonium polyhalides are widely used as halogenating reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. Recently, tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) has been used for the bromination of some selected organic substrates⁴. There are, however, only a few reports regarding their use as oxidizing and brominating agents in synthetic chemistry⁵⁻⁷. These compounds are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yields. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of polyhalides and many reports (including TBATB) have already emanated from our laboratory⁸⁻¹⁰. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of thioacids by TBATB. Therefore, in continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation studies by polyhalides, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of thioglycolic (TGA), thiolactic (TLA) and thiomalic (TMA) by TBATB in acetic acid. Mechanistic aspects have also discussed.

Table 1 Rate constants for the oxidation of thioacids by TBATB at 298 K

10^3 [TBATB] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Thioacid] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)		
		TGA	TLA	TMA
1.0	0.10	2.05	9.08	5.36
1.0	0.20	3.27	14.6	8.21
1.0	0.40	4.64	20.9	11.3
1.0	0.60	5.40	24.5	12.9
1.0	0.80	5.88	26.8	14.0
1.0	1.50	6.71	30.8	15.7
1.0	3.00	7.30	33.6	16.8
2.0	0.40	4.86	21.7	11.9
4.0	0.40	4.22	19.9	10.6
6.0	0.40	4.53	20.4	11.2
8.0	0.40	4.70	21.2	10.8
1.0	0.20	3.32 ^a	14.8 ^a	8.37 ^a

^aContained 0.001 M acrylonitrile

Results and discussion

Rate laws :

The reactions are of first order with respect to TBATB. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order in TBATB. Further, the first order rate coefficients did not vary the initial concentration of the TBATB. The order with respect to the thioacid is less than one (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{thioacid}]$ is linear with an intercept at the rate ordinate. Thus Michaelis-Menten type kinetics are observed with respect to the thioacid. This leads to the postulation of the following overall mechanism (1) and (2) and the rate law (3).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{thioacid}] [\text{TBATB}] / (1 + K [\text{thioacid}]) \quad (3)$$

The dependence of the concentration of thioacid was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and the activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively at different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of thioacids by TBATB, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus a one electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

Table 2. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the thioacids-TBATB complexes

Subst.	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
TGA	4.26	3.45	2.72	2.09	-20.5 ± 0.7	-51 ± 2	-5.51 ± 0.5
TLA	3.96	3.24	2.56	1.91	-20.9 ± 0.9	-53 ± 3	-5.34 ± 0.8
TMA	5.04	4.11	3.20	2.43	-21.0 ± 0.8	-51 ± 3	-5.93 ± 0.7

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters for the disproportionation of thioacid-TBATB complexes

Subst.	$10^4 k_2/s^{-1}$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
TGA	4.32	8.01	14.1	25.2	42.1 ± 0.4	-164 ± 1	90.7 ± 0.3
TLA	21.6	37.1	66.8	117	40.5 ± 0.8	-156 ± 3	86.8 ± 0.6
TMA	10.4	18.2	33.3	56.7	40.8 ± 0.6	-161 ± 2	88.6 ± 0.5

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of three thioacids were determined at four different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride : Addition of tetrabutylammonium chloride (TBACl) or bromide ions had no effect on the rates of oxidation (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride on the rate of oxidation of thioglycolic acid by TBATB

[TBTAB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , [TGA] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 308 K							
10^3 [TBACl] mol dm ⁻³	0.00	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00	
$10^4 k_{obs}/s^{-1}$	14.1	13.8	14.5	14.0	13.3	13.1	

Effect of potassium bromide : The rate of oxidation of thioglycolic acid (TGA) decreases with increase in the concentration of potassium bromide but reaches a limiting value at [KBr] ≈ 0.16 mol dm⁻³ (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of potassium bromide on the rate of oxidation of thioglycolic acid by TBATB

[TBTAB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , [TGA] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 288 K							
[KBr] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.12	0.16	0.20	0.40
$10^4 k_{obs}/s^{-1}$	21.1	19.4	17.5	15.0	14.2	13.5	14.3

We have carried out some conductivity measurements to determine the nature of TBATB in aqueous acetic acid solution. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of TBATB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of TBATB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. We found that the conductivity increases sharply as the water content is initially increased but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. TBATB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under our reaction conditions as tetrabutylammonium and tribromide ions as shown in eq. (4). No effect of added tetrabutylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (4) lies far towards the right. Similar results were obtained in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes

by TBATB¹⁰. Thus in the present reaction also the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to bromine and bromide ion [eq. (5)] and the value of the dissociation constant has been reported¹¹. The oxidation of alcohol by bromine is reported to be much faster¹² as compared to this reaction. The effect of addition of bromide ion (*cf.* Table 5) indicated that as the [Br⁻] increases, the concentration of bromine and its contribution to the oxidation of benzyl alcohol decrease and become almost negligible at [KBr] ≈ 0.16 mol dm⁻³. As a large excess (0.2 mol dm⁻³) of bromide ion has been added in present reaction, the oxidation due to bromine will be suppressed. Thus in the present reaction the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

Mechanism :

The lack of any effect of radical scavenger such as acrylonitrile on the reaction rate and the failure to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile point against the operation of a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals. The observed Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to the thioacid lead us to suggest that an intermediate complex may be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pairs of electrons of thioacid-sulphur and tribromide ion in a rapid pre-equilibrium. Heasley and co-workers¹³ proposed that a complex might be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pairs of electrons of the alcohol-oxygen and tribromide ion. The formation of similar complexes has also been postulated in the oxidation of aldehydes¹⁴ and diols¹⁵ with hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) as well as in the oxidation of alcohols¹⁶ and organic acids¹⁷ by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB). The formation of moderately stable complexes is supported by the values of thermodynamic parameters also. The complex formation is favoured by the enthalpy term

but there is a loss of entropy indicating the formation of a rigid structure. The present experimental results can be accounted by a mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate in a rapid pre-equilibrium in the rate-determining step to form a sulfenium cation.

The observed negative entropy of activation also supports the above mechanism. As the charge separation takes place, in the transition state of the rate-determining step, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilisation of large number solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy¹⁸. The low value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and the large value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ indicate that the reaction entropy controlled. The low value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ also shows that in the rate-determining step bond-breaking and bond-formation are of almost equal in magnitude.

Experimental

Materials :

The thioacids (Fluka) and dithiodiglycollic acid (Evan Chemicals, USA) were commercial products and were used as such. Dithiodimalic and dithiodilactic acids were prepared by the oxidation of the corresponding thiols by ferric alum¹⁹. The solutions of the thioacids were freshly prepared in acetic acid and were standardized by titrating them against a standard solution of iodine^{19,20}. TBATB was prepared by the reported method¹ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionated²¹.

Stoichiometry :

Stoichiometric determinations, as well as the characterization of the products, carried out polarographically^{22,23} using an automatic (Heyrovsky TP 55A). It was found that the cathode wave given by a known sample of disulphide dimmer coincided by the wave given by the final product of the oxidation. The reaction exhibited a 1 : 2 stoichiometry, i.e. 2 moles of the thiol are oxidized per mole of TBATB reduced. Further, the reaction mixtures with an excess of TBATB were allowed to go to completion and the residual TBATB was determined iodometrically. These results also gave a 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

Kinetic measurements :

The reactions were carried out under pseudo first-order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the thioacids over TBATB. The solvent was glacial acetic acid, unless specified otherwise. Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to a large extent to bromine and bromide ion. The value¹¹ of the dissociation constant in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water is *ca.* 0.02 mol dm^{-3} . To suppress the dissociation, all kinetic runs were carried out in the presence of an excess (0.2 mol dm^{-3}) of potassium bromide. The reactions were carried out in flasks blackened from the outside to prevent any photochemical reactions and were followed up to *ca.* 80% conversion by monitoring the decrease in the [TBATB] at 356 nm on a spectrophotometer (AIMIL, India, Model MK-II). The pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear least-squares plots of $\log [\text{TBATB}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants were evaluated from the relation $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{reductant}]$.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support and to Professor K. K. Banerji for valuable suggestions.

References

- 1 S Kajigaeshi, T Kakinami, T Okamoto and S Fujisaki, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1987, **60**, 1159
- 2 S Kajigaeshi, T Kakinami, H Yamasaki, S Fujisaki and T Okamoto, *Bull Chem Soc. Jpn*, 1988, **61**, 2681
- 3 S Kajigaeshi, T Kakinami, T. Okamoto, M Nakahara and M Fujikawa, *Bull Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1987, **60**, 4187
- 4 M K Choudhary, A T Khan and B K Patel, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1998, **39**, 8163
- 5 J Berthalot, C Guette, M Ouchefoune, P L. Desbens and J J Basseher, *J Chem Res (S)*, 1986, 381, *Synth Commun*, 1986, **16**, 1641
- 6 S Kajigaeshi, H Kawamuki and S Fujisaki, *Bull. Chem Soc. Jpn*, 1989, **62**, 2585
- 7 S Kajigaeshi, Y Morikawa, S Fujisaki, T. Kakinami and K Nishihira, *Bull Chem Soc. Jpn*, 1989, **64**, 336
- 8 A Bohra, P K Sharma and K K Banerji, *J. Chem Res.*, 1999, (S) 308, (M) 1343
- 9 V S R Raju, P K Sharma and K K Banerji, *J Org Chem*, 2000, **39A**, 1258
- 10 M Baghmar and P K Sharma, *Int J Chem Kinet*, 2001, **33**, 390
- 11 A E Bradfield, B Jones and K J P Orton, *J. Chem. Soc*, 1929, 2810
- 12 K K Banerji, *Indian J Chem*, 1973, **11**, 244
- 13 V L Heasley, T J Louie, D K Luttrul, M D Miller, H B Moore, D F Nogales, A M Saucibrey, A B Shevel, T Y

Chouhan *et al.* : Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some thioacids by tetrabutylammonium *etc.*

- Shibuya, M. S. Stanley, D. F. Shellhamer and G. E. Heasley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 2199.
14. A. Pareek, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1997, **60**, 127.
15. H. Gangwani, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1999, (S) 180; (M) 854.
16. D. Mathur, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1993, 205.
17. D. Suri, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1996, (S) 228; (M) 1301.
18. E. S. Gould, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc., New York, 1964.
19. D. L. Leussing and I. M. Kolthoff, *Electrochem. Soc.*, 1953, **100**, 334.
20. H. Krammer, *J. Assoc. of Agric. Chem.*, 1952, **35**, 385.
21. D. D. Perrin, W. L. Armarego and D. R. Perrin, "Purification of Organic Compounds", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1966.
22. R. C. Kapoor, O. P. Kachhwaha and B. P. Sinha, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 1627.
23. R. C. Kapoor, O. P. Kachhwaha and B. P. Sinha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 499.